

Coronavirus And Covid-19: A Brief Overview

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Introduction

Covid -19 pandemic hit the human population in late 2019. It is still continuing in different forms. Even though the severity and infectivity vary from time to time and from region to region, an exhaustive knowledge and insight into its cause, origin, transmission, pathophysiology, diagnosis, prevention strategies and zoonotic aspects is essential to be studied. Therefore, this review focuses on these aspects and emphasizes the need for future aspects towards containment of this pandemic and curtail its spread.

What is coronavirus?

Coronavirus is enveloped, positive sense, single stranded RNA entities that fall under largest genome of RNA virus that is characterized by club / petal shaped projections on outer surface. Coronavirus is having diameter of approximately 100-160nm and size of 27-32kb, which tends to infect both, human as well as animals. Club / petal shaped projections which are present on the virus surface gives this virus appearance like crown (Latin meaning *corona*) (Wikipedia, 2020).

Classification of coronavirus

Coronavirus falls under *Nidovirales* order, *Coronaviridae* family, *Coronavirinae* sub family. Coronavirus has four genera namely: *Alphacoronavirus*, *Betacoronavirus*, *Gammacoronavirus* and *Deltacoronavirus*. *Alphacoronavirus* only affects animals while *Betacoronavirus* affects human and *Gammacoronavirus* affects birds. Current pandemic SARS-CoV-2 falls under *Betacoronavirus* (Wikipedia, 2020).

SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19

SARS-CoV-2 is the name of the virus which stands for severe acute respiratory syndrome-Coronavirus- 2, which falls under *Betacoronavirus* genera, having 30 kb size of an 120 nm diameter while COVID-19 is the name of the disease caused by SARS-CoV-2 virus. SARS-CoV-2 is responsible for causing mild infection to SARS in human population which is known as, COVID-19, which stands for Coronavirus Disease- 19 (Chan *et al.*, 2019).

Structure of SARS-COV-2

Spike ‘S’-Protein

This protein is anchored on virus envelope which gives this virus crown-like appearance. Functionally, it is required for virus attachment and entry inside the host cell. The ectodomain in all coronaviruses S protein shows a similar domain organization, divided into two domains. The first one, S1, helps in host receptor binding while the second one, S2, is responsible for the fusion.

Membrane ‘M’-Protein

The M protein is the most abundant viral protein present in the virion particle, gives a definite shape to the viral envelope. It binds to nucleocapsid and acts as a central organizer of the coronavirus assembly. The M protein has three transmembrane domains, flanked by short amino terminal outside the virion and a long carboxy-terminal inside the virion.

Envelope ‘E’-Protein

The coronavirus E protein is the most enigmatic and smallest among the major structural proteins. It plays a multifunctional role in the pathogenesis, assembly, and release of the virus and acts as viroporin (Ion channel).

Nucleocapsid ‘N’-Protein

The N protein of coronavirus is for multipurpose. Among several functions, it plays a role in complex formation with viral genome, facilitates M protein interaction needed during virion assembly and enhances transcription efficiency of the virus.

Haemagglutinin esterase ‘HE’-Protein

HE-Protein plays role as receptor destroying enzyme (RDE) (Tian *et al.*, 2020).

Transmission

The origin still cannot be affirmed but has been attributed to seafood market in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. Live animal market seems to be nidus of this virus as they may act as intermediate host. This increases the possibility of zoonotic disease transmission to humans. As in other respiratory viruses, transmission is more likely by direct contact, shaking contaminated hands, or by direct

contact with contaminated surfaces. Older people with an underlying chronic disease are more likely to become severely infected. Both the asymptomatic and symptomatic patients secrete similar viral load, which indicates that the transmission capacity of asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic patients is very high. This reflects that the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (2019-nCoV) may occur early in the course of infection.

Pathophysiology

The 2019-novel-CoV invades lung parenchyma resulting in severe inflammation of interstitium the lungs. This is evident on CT images as ground-glass opacity observed in the lungs. This lesion, even though in initial phase involves a single lobe inflammation, which is lobar pneumonia but later expands to multiple lobes of the lungs which is bronchopneumonia (Zhou and Liu, 2020). Lung biopsy from COVID-19 in histology shows diffuse alveolar damage of lungs, cellular fibromyxoid exudates, hyaline membrane formation and desquamation of pneumocells characteristic of ARDS. Cytokine storms associated with exaggerated immune response can even lead to multiple organ failure later. Albumin, lactate dehydrogenase, C-reactive protein, lymphocytes (%), and neutrophils (%) in blood may reflect diversity of disease. It has also been found that the patients infected with by SARS-CoV-2 does often have lymphocytopenia along with or without leukocyte abnormalities. The degree of lymphocytopenia gives an actual idea about the disease prognosis as it is found positively correlated with the disease severity (Zhou and Liu, 2020).

There are few reports that indicate pregnant women may be at high risk of getting infected by COVID-19 that further may result in adverse outcomes for foetus. The possibility of intrauterine maternal-fetal transmission (vertical transmission) of coronaviruses is low, and not confirmed.

Clinical signs in humans

Clinical signs observed in people affected by SARS-CoV-2 includes sore throat, headache, fever (40°C), dry cough, shortness of breath, fatigue.

Diagnosis

Reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) is considered as an effective method for confirming the diagnosis in clinical cases of COVID-19. It can also be confirmed by isolation and culturing of samples such as sputum, nasopharyngeal or oropharyngeal swab, blood, stool and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid. Chest CT (Progressive test) is an ideal diagnostic tool for identifying virus-induced pneumonia and patchy infiltration that later turns into ground glass opacities may be characteristic to COVID-19.

Therapy and vaccination

Antiviral drugs

These drugs prevent viral replication through various mechanisms, including blocking SARS-CoV-2 entry, inhibiting the activity of SARS-CoV-2 3-chymotrypsin-like protease (3CLpro) and RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) and causing lethal viral mutagenesis. **Remdesivir is the only antiviral drug that is approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of COVID-19.** Anti-SARS-CoV-2 therapies as preferred treatments for COVID-19 is **Ritonavir-boosted Nirmatrelvir.** Anti-SARS-CoV-2 therapies as alternative treatments for COVID-19. These drugs should **only** be used when neither of the preferred treatments are available, feasible to use, or clinically appropriate like, Bectelovimab, Molnupiravir, Interferon alfa or beta or lambda for hospitalized patients, Ivermectin, Nitazoxanide, chloroquine or hydroxychloroquine and/or azithromycin for hospitalized and nonhospitalized patients, Lopinavir/ritonavir and other HIV protease inhibitors. Ritonavir-boosted nirmatrelvir (Paxlovid), molnupiravir, and certain anti-SARS-CoV-2 monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) have received Emergency Use Authorizations from the FDA for the treatment of COVID-19. Antiviral drugs like, Oseltamivir, acyclovir, ganciclovir and ribavirin was previously used in 2002 and 2012 coronavirus outbreaks. First ever use of Oseltamivir was done in initial outbreak of SARS-CoV-2 in China.

Inhalation corticosteroids

Corticosteroids through inhalation route like, Ciclesonide is used which helps in reduction of viral replication, pulmonary inflammation and lowers immunosuppressive effects, when compared to systematic corticosteroids. Another Inhalation corticosteroid like, budesonide is also tested but it is not effective as ciclesonide. Inhaled budesonide improves time to recovery, with a chance of also reducing hospital admissions or deaths, in people with COVID-19 in the community who are at higher risk of complications (Yu *et al.*, 2022).

Vaccines

Few examples of vaccines that are approved for use are [AstraZeneca/Oxford vaccine](#) (Oxford University and British-Swedish company AstraZeneca), [Johnson and Johnson](#) (Janssen Pharmaceutical), Spikevax ([Moderna](#)), [Pfizer/BionTech](#), [Sinopharm](#) (Beijing Bio-Institute of Biological Products) [Sinovac](#)- Sinovac Biotech Ltd) [COVAXIN](#) (Bharat Biotech), COVISHIELD (Serum Institute of India Pvt Ltd), ZyCoV-D (Zydus Cadila) and Nuvaxovid and Covovax ([Nuvaxovid](#)).

Coronavirus in animals and zoonotic links

Bovine coronavirus

In adult mammals, coronavirus shows winter dysentery like signs and symptoms, anorexia, depression, dehydration, reduced weight gain and diarrhoea. While in young animals, coronavirus produces serous to purulent nasal discharge.

Canine enteric coronavirus

Coronavirus in canine is associated with diarrhoea and vomiting.

SADS-CoV

SADS-CoV stands for Severe Acute Diarrhoeal Syndrome which is caused by coronavirus in pigs, mainly in piglets, in which suckling piglets had encountered with severe enteritis as well as death.

SARS-CoV-2

There are reports of spread of coronavirus infection in cats and dogs from China and Italy as these pets' owner got COVID-19 infection. Three lions and four tigers of New York Zoo also been tested positive along with zoo keeper. In Netherlands, Minks got infected simultaneous to farm keeper.

Prevention and control

As there is dearth of specific and effective treatment, prevention and control is the only way of handling the covid-19 pandemic. Use of face masks, avoiding close contact, sanitizing hands regularly, isolating the infected individuals, vaccination, improving general health and immunity are some of the ways that may help in reducing the spread of infection.

Care of animals

As zoonotic aspects yet have to be established, meanwhile good care of animals can be taken by isolating them from infected persons, sanitizing their surroundings, regular health check may be of help in preventing the disease.

Conclusion

COVID-19 is a pandemic caused by a coronavirus of β genera named as SARS-CoV-2 virus. The causative virus can be easily transmitted from infected persons. It affects primarily respiratory system and finally can affect other organs resulting in death. Specific and effective treatment is still evolving. Prevention by covid appropriate behaviour and vaccination is currently the best possible way to contain the spread of disease. Diagnosis and isolation are key to protect healthy individuals from infected ones. Improved general health and immunity may be of help to avoid serious illness.

Future prospects

Effective vaccines and treatment strategies are required. More infrastructure facilities are needed for isolating the infected individuals and providing medical support for recuperation. Policies should ensure One health around the globe.

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